

Knowledge Representation and Neuroscience

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RESEARCH SYNOPSIS

KNOWLEDGE REPRESENTATION, AN INTRODUCTION

MULTIDISCIPLINARY PERSPECTIVE

INTERSECTIONS WITH NEUROSCIENCE

NEW FINDINGS

OPEN RESEARCH AVENUES

WORK AHEAD

KNOWLEDGE
REPRESENTATION
COGNITION
cONSCIOUSNESS

BACKGROUND: Complexity Science , Information Theory, Knowledge
Integration -

MOTIVATION: Neuroscience is the ultimate
frontier, relevant to many other fields

Facilitate Learning/Education

Enable the evaluation of research claims

Development of New technologies and methods

Initial questions

It is said that NN/ML are inspired by brain but I found no tangible commonality between datasets

What K from BNN can help to research/model/develop ANNs? (for example, *spikes*).

Not easy to answer. Despite decades of research and a lot of data available the answer is not straightforward/explicit because.... fragmentation

<https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2020.06.26.174482v1>

We evaluated a broad range of state-of-the-art ANN models on the match of their internal representations to three human 84 neural datasets. The models spanned all major classes of existing language models and included embedding models (e.g., 85 GloVe (Pennington et al., 2014)), recurrent neural networks (e.g., LM1B (Jozefowicz et al., 2016)), and variants of attention⁸⁶ based architectures—transformers (e.g., BERT (Devlin et al., 2018), XLM (Lample & Conneau, 2019), GPT (Radford et al., 87 2019), and T5 (Raffel et al., 2019)) (Methods₅, Table S10)

"One key missing piece in the mechanistic modeling of human language processing is a more detailed mapping from model components onto brain anatomy. In particular, aside from the general targeting of the fronto-temporal language network, it is unclear which parts of a model map onto which components of the brain's language processing mechanisms. In models of vision, for instance, attempts are made to map ANN layers and neurons onto cortical regions (Kubilius et al., 2019) and sub-regions (Lee & DiCarlo, 2018). However, whereas function and its mapping onto anatomy is at least coarsely defined in the case of vision (Felleman & Van Essen, 1991), a similar mapping is not yet established in language beyond the broad distinction between perceptual processing and higher-level linguistic interpretation (Fedorenko & Thompson-Schill, 2014)."

Why Open and Shared?

YOu know this of course

Explicit, Explainable,
Trustworthy

Understandable

Verifiable/Reproducible

Less Resources Intensive

Interoperable/

Interdisciplinary

Issues

To learn from NS (for AI, Neuromorphic etc) we need to understand brain data.

The Brain is the most complex and advanced information processing entity.

PROBLEM: Lack of Alignment/Mapping/Interpretability in datasets

a) internal alignment (within NS branches)

b) external (between NS and say, AI/SE)

Usual misalignment issues, different vocabularies, concepts etc, Common in other fields

Many different standards for NS/Brain Data

NEUROML

BIDS

NWB 2.- (neurodata without borders) etc

Some parts of these standards may differ, some may overlap

Problems: usual fragmentation

offer different views /not interoperable

strongly coupled with software/environments (ie python)

current standards mostly reflect data/file formats, not developed following proper modelling

viewable via python compiler-

not available as visual/document or schema, limited usability

Knowledge Representation

Symbolic, Non Symbolic, Neurosymbolic (from AI)

Conceptual Entities

Structural Models

Relations

Logic

Chek out KR
good practices
in literature

Approaches

Computational/Theoretical/Simulation

Cognitive

Systemic (integrated)

Applied

KR in AI/ML - NEW ROLES

Natural Language KR, also referred to as symbolic KR, can also be useful to

- ensure that systemic bias is identified and contained/mitigated
- ensures the preservation of truth values across permutations (as in Neural Networks and Machine Learning)
- ensures semantic precision and consistency throughout the system's lifecycle

Methods integration - Learning from Neighbouring Disciplines

Starting point is Knowledge Representation (from AI)

Combine approaches from:

Systems biology (Shinsuke Uda, Kyushu University)

Transomics,

Bioinformatics (BLAST)

Examples of related work being done

Functional connectivity research

Dynamic cognition and behaviour

Related Research

(Images taken from the references)

Reid, A.T., Headley, D.B., Mill, R.D. *et al.* Advancing functional connectivity research from association to causation. *Nat Neurosci* 22, 1751–1760 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41593-019-0510-4>

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Example of Multilevel data schema

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3709834/>

Extended system boundary: Research data is typically from one area of study

Disconnected models: $q(X, Y)$

$$\min_q D_{KL}(p||q)$$

Full model: $p(X, Y)$

(a) Mutual information

(b) Transfer entropy

(c) Integrated information

(d) Stochastic interaction

INFORMATION GEOMETRY

MY AREA OF WORK

To facilitate transformation/mapping between datasets and schemas

To enable natural language querying of brain data

To make neuroscience research data available and relevant to other disciplines >>>>fields of application incl social sciences

To create learning resources that are in synch with research

WORK TO BE DONE

Neuroscientists and Programmers already doing great work

however

Not enough ontologists/analyst/systemists in the mix

High Level/meta-analysis view in Brain Data not yet there

Roadmap (broad strokes)

Identify and map standards

Scope

Selects methods (from Ontology Alignment/Information Theory)

Apply methods to subset of corpus

Evaluate

Iterate

Thanks, Questions? Get in Touch

Thank You To The Many People Who Are Doing Incredible Work Already To Allow Newcomers To Make Sense Of The Languages And Data, And Making It Available Online = NIMH Data Archive, OpenNeuro etc

Good Research Data is Produced And Published Everyday, But Cognitive and Training Barriers To Use This Data Are Very High and Costly to overcome

Shared and explicit KR can advance the state of the art across sciences, make learning and verification easier

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